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European forum and oBServatory for OPEN science in transport

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D6.5 Project video

Final

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Executive summary

The present deliverable is part of the Work Package 6 “Dissemination and Engagement”. To create awareness and achieve the objectives stated, the consortium has defined under Task 6.2 “Dissemination Activities and events” [1], the development of the BE OPEN project video.

Originally, the video was planned to be produced at the beginning of the project. However, after further consideration and discussion at the project kick-off meeting, the Partners agreed to postpone the production to the end of the project, in view to use this tool for the final dissemination activities, with a strong focus on the project outcomes, notably the TOPOS, for further exploitation of results. Such change was agreed by the Project Officer/INEA and therefore the due date of the video and related deliverable were postponed from month 8 to month 28.

A video was chosen to visually bring the project key messages across and to illustrate the project’s achievements. This tool provides a highly scalable and cost-effective communication that can reach a wide audience and various stakeholders on the devices of their choice, in a simple and efficient manner.

It is planned to be shown for the first time at the project final event, and then broadly disseminated in the following weeks.

The video development process and content are further described in the present deliverable.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
TOPOS	Transport Observatory/fOrum for Promoting Open Science
WP	Work Package

Partners' Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Partner/Third Parties' name
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
ARC	Athena Research and Innovation Center In Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies
BME	Budapest University of Technology and Economics
CDV	Transport Research Centre
CERTH-HIT	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Hellenic Institute of Transport
DLR	German Aerospace Center / Deutsches Zentrum für Luft - und Raumfahrt EV
EATEO	European Association of Aviation Training and Education Organizations
ECTRI	European Conference of Transport Research Institutes
EURNEX	EUropean rail Research Network of EXcellence
FEHRL	Forum Européen des Laboratoires Nationaux de Recherche Routière
FIT	FIT Consulting Srl
FTTE	The Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, University of Belgrade
GUT	Gdańsk University of Technology
HUMANIST	HUMANIST VCE
KT	Konnekt-able Technologies Ltd.
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens

Osborne Clarke	Osborne Clarke Anwaltssozietat
SCIPEDIA	SCIPEDIA S.L.
Strathclyde University	Strathclyde University
TØI	Transportøkonomisk Institutt
UITP	Union Internationale des Transports Publics
VDI/VDE	VDI/VDE Innovation + Technik GmbH
VGTU	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University
WEGEMT	Foundation Wegemt - A European Association of Universities in Marine Technology and Related Sciences

2 INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable is part of the WP6 “Dissemination and Engagement” [1], which aims to:

- Disseminate key project outputs to key actors and transport stakeholders;
- Implement and regularly update an appropriate online presence (web-site, social media, EOOSC integration) and other relevant dissemination material to ensure continuous outreach of the project outcomes, as well as transfer of knowledge;
- Organise project key events and ensure cooperation with the most important international forums, as well as liaise with related projects and initiatives. Demonstrate the economic viability and lay the foundations for subsequent exploitation;
- Engage publishing companies and set up communication tools/actions;
- Supervise project results and key outcomes through the external Advisory Board.

To create awareness and achieve the objectives above stated, the consortium has defined under T6.2 “Dissemination Activities and events” [1], the development of the BE OPEN project video. This communication tool will be presented and described in the present deliverable.

3 VIDEO

The BE OPEN video aims to visually bring the project key messages across and illustrate the project’s achievements. This tool provides a highly scalable and cost-effective communication that can reach a wider audience and various stakeholders on the devices of their choice, in a simple and efficient manner.

This video will be used for the final dissemination activities with a strong focus on the main project outcomes i.e. notably the TOPOS, the framework of common understanding for realizing Open Science services in transport research, the Code of Conduct for implementing Open Science principles in transport research in Europe, KPIs for evaluating transport research that uses Open Science. For further exploitation of the BE OPEN results, the video is planned to be shown for the first time at the project final event and then broadly disseminated in the following weeks.

3.1 Type, style and references

The video type chosen is motion graphics, which translates as animation, with text as a major component. Animation was privileged to live action video, as it works best for presenting abstract ideas, simplifying complex topics and bring them to life, while engaging with the audience.

The video follows the script, with a clever way of visual storytelling, linking back to the BE OPEN and TOPOS visual identity (logo and colours) [2].

The video is complemented with subtitles in English, making the content accessible to a larger audience, including deaf or hard-of-hearing viewers. The subtitles also help viewers remember and retain facts, and even integrate these concepts into their vocabulary.

3.2 Duration, script and storyboard

In terms of length, the video is about 180 seconds. It is concise and strive to capture viewers' interest in the first few seconds. Therefore, information is condensed down into easily digestible snippets of content that is long enough to maintain viewers' attention and pass the message. At the same time, it is short enough to incite viewers to look for more information.

The script was drafted in two stages. First, the key messages from the project results and outputs were summarized by the WP leaders and partners responsible for the development of TOPOS. Then, those ideas were incorporated in the final script by the leader of the Dissemination and Engagement WP with support of the coordinator.

The final script (text in bold) and storyboard (images and description in *italic*) are presented below, step by step.

Figure 1

Open Science is a new approach to practice science.

We start the video with the appearing of text on screen (TOS). A circle and particles appear around it, as well as a scribbled notification.

Figure 2

It increases openness,...

TOS changes to a new scribbled one, and the particles change from closed to open circles.

Figure 3

...integrity and...

TOS changes again. We see the circles again... with 1 triangle! But luckily, that one quickly becomes a circle too (as its integer).

Figure 4

...reproducibility of research.

TOS changes again, and a lot more particles appear.

Figure 5

By doing so, it helps make scientific results and processes...

We now start developing the logo in different steps: first, we see the particles taking their correct place.

Figure 6

...more transparent,...

Step 2: the gradient appears.

Figure 7

...and accessible to everyone, at all levels.

Step 3: the connecting lines appear.

Figure 8

To support the implementation of Open Science
in the transport domain, at a European level,...

Step 4: we see the means of transportation.

Figure 9

...the BE OPEN project was launched.

And finally, we can read the name too.

Figure 10

And in two years time,...

*We zoom out and see the logo on a two-year
timeline.*

Figure 11

...the project achieved three important results.
As the logo progresses, 3 flags pop up.

Figure 12

One. It established a common understanding of Open Science in transport research.

Flag 1 appears in the upper left corner. We see a document representing the common understanding, and we read "Open science in transport research" scribbled. Both on and off the page, we see visual elements that represent what is considered to be part of the common understanding (on the page), and what is not (next to the page).

Figure 13

Two. It engaged the key transport stakeholders...

Flag 2. A particles moves in between the means of transportation, touching them.

Figure 14

...and created a necessary framework,...

And finally it draws up a rectangle as a frame, surrounding them.

Figure 15

...with legal specifications for Code of Conduct on Open Science and Key Performance Indicators for evaluating transport research that uses Open Science.

In the frame, two stacks of documents appear: we read code of conduct and evaluation KPI's, scribbled.

Figure 16

Three. It built a solid knowledge base on how to implement Open Science approaches,...

Flag 3. A brain appears, with a scribbled side note.

Figure 17

...and proposed a roadmap to promote Open Science in transport research.

Next to the brain, a doc appears, again with a designating side note ("roadmap").

Figure 18

In addition to these three achievements, the project set up the TOPOS forum and observatory.

We zoom out and go back to the timeline, where the TOPOS logo appeared too, with two side notes.

Figure 19

This online platform is a single-entry point to explore, share and discuss research knowledge, data, publications, software and other information relevant to transport and mobility research.

We now go to a layout, where we can read 3 items as TOS, and see some tiles with visuals: a brain, a matrix, a doc, a cloud/download icon, and 3 pulsating dots (representing "other information").

Figure 20

It's completely customized for transport research organisations on the one hand,...

We move to a split-screen: on the left, we still see the layout, but from the right a new scene slides in, showing the means of transportation.

Figure 21

...and individuals on the other hand.

The scenes slide to the left, revealing a new one on the right: a silhouette.

Figure 22

Offering different services depending on the user.

The layout reappears, but is also split: on the left, we see the Organisations' view, on the right that of the Individuals. A scribbled cursor moves across the screen.

Figure 23

Companies, universities and research centers can use the TOPOS Observatory for organisations to access a vast number of research outputs related to transport research, which all follow open science guidelines and best practices by design.

We focus on the Organisations, and "Observatory" is scribbled. On the left, the different categories are now readable as TOS, on the right we see the vast amount of output that is available with the numbers even going up as we speak.

Figure 24

The platform is also linked to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and connected to the services of OpenAIRE.

On the right, both logos appear, with sketched arrows.

Figure 25

The TOPOS Observatory for individuals offers an open professional network where experts in transport science and technology, professors, researchers and students can share and access knowledge and their scientific work.

We now focus on the individuals, where the categories can be read too, on the right. On the left, a network of brains connected to docs appears.

Figure 26

This part of the platform is also open to citizens who are interested in learning more about transport research.

A fourth category is being scribbled on the right (citizens), along with a sketched arrow and a big circle around the network.

Figure 27

Lastly, the TOPOS platform provides a Forum, to exchange ideas and share best practices for operationalising Open Science principles in transport research.

We now go back to a full layout and scribbled "Forum". On the platform, we see a bunch of text balloons appearing and disappearing again, to represent the exchanging of thoughts and ideas.

#openscience #transportation #research
#explore #share #discuss

Figure 28

Want to be part of this amazing journey of open and collaborative research in transport?

We slowly zoom out to see TOPOS logo and key ideas as hashtags.

Visit topos-observatory.eu

Figure 29

Visit topos-observatory.eu.

Finally, the url appears along with a moving sketched cursor. The end.

3.3 Production

Technical specifications (so called "cahier des charges") detailing the video requirements and conditions - available as [Appendix I](#) - were prepared by the Dissemination and Engagement leader and sent to five companies specialised in web and audio-visual.

A company called “[Well Played](#)” was selected among all others for their middle range and client-oriented offer, technical resources, and portfolio. A teleconference between Well Played and ECTRI team, the dissemination leader, took place on April 20, 2021, to agree on the final plans and timeline.

Well Played then undertook the motion design video production e.g. storyboard, style, animation, music, sound effects and voice-over. Each stage was reviewed by ECTRI and validated until final production.

The planning for developing the video was the following:

Figure 30

3.4 Video output

The BE OPEN video is available online under the BE OPEN YouTube account.

Video URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g9x6kUn_c9s&t=4s

3.5 Dissemination

Having a strong focus on the project outcomes, notably the TOPOS, the video will be first presented at the BE OPEN final event, on June 9th, 2021.

Afterwards, the video will be widely disseminated on the BE OPEN website and social media [3], the BE OPEN newsletter and across the BE OPEN partners’ media. The BE OPEN partners will also be invited to upload the video to their platforms.

Other opportunities will be explored towards relevant stakeholders’ events, such as the joint event “BE OPEN meets OSCAR”, the EOSC platform and others.

4 REFERENCES

- [1] BE OPEN Grant Agreement (824323 — H2020-MG-2018-2019-2020/H2020-MG-2018-SingleStage-INEA)
- [2] BE OPEN D6.1 Project logo and website (public)
- [3] BE OPEN D6.4 Social media (public)

Appendix I - Cahier des charges /Technical specifications

BE OPEN PROJECT VIDEO/ REQUEST FOR QUOTE *Technical specifications / Cahier des charges*

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2.2. Script lines

1. Intro: Partners gathered to promote, regulate and standardise open science in transport
2. Project finding and outputs; highlight on [Transport fOrum / Observatory for Promoting Open Science \(TOPOS\)](#)
3. Societal impact: Unique selling point(s) of TOPOS

Script is currently being drafted by the partners.

2.3. First ideas

- Animation video with voice over / storytelling style
- Use the BE OPEN logo and as driver for the animation
- Use testimonials from developers (project partners) and potential users

As most first ideas they are open for discussion.

2.4. EU funding

For the BE OPEN project the text below and EU flag shall be used in the requested communication and dissemination material.

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3. COPYRIGHT

The provider assigns to BE OPEN the copyright on the whole of the productions delivered. All source files, necessary for the update of design, shall also be delivered in exploitable formats.

4. TIMELINE and QUOTE

Under the frame of the Grant Agreement signed between the partners and the European Commission, we are bounded to strict budget and time schedule.

The video is expected to be produced and delivered by the end of May (the latest) with a budget of 5.000 EUR, with a margin of 2.000 EUR.

For the services requested, **please provide a quote and work timeline, from proposal to delivery.**

Please feel free to present us examples of your work that you think might fit out needs.

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1. The BE OPEN project

The BE OPEN project is a Horizon 2020 coordination and support action aiming at "Promoting, regulating and standardising Open Science in Transport". <https://beopen-project.eu/>

1.1. Visual brand

The logo illustrates the project's scope and vision:

- The **transport research** is represented by the modes/means of transport
- The sphere stands for a lens representing the **transparency, openness, fairness and reproducibility of science**
- The dots and intersecting lines represent the **knowledge shared and developed through collaborative networks**

Figure 1. BE OPEN logo

1.2. Audience

Primary audience

- Universities and R&D Institutes (students, researchers and management staff)
- Transport and Open Science related networks
- Industry (transportation related industry and SMEs)
- Publishing portals and houses; indexation companies
- Policy makers; European Commission and related agencies; other EU bodies

Secondary audience

- General public (citizens)

2. VIDEO (project)

2.1. Characteristics

- Short length (2 to 3 minutes)
- To be uploaded to platforms: YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn
- Mandatory elements: BE OPEN logo and EU flag and acknowledge of funding (see section 2.4)

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5. CONTACT

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